

KNOWLEDGE REGARDING HOARDING DISORDER AMONG STUDENTS OF JAIPUR NURSING COLLEGE, JAIPUR RAJASTHAN IN A VIEW TO DEVELOP AN INFORMATION BOOKLET

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ABSTRACT

The study was conducted to assess the knowledge regarding hoarding disorder among students of Jaipur Nursing College, Jaipur Rajasthan in a view to develop an information booklet. A descriptive study design was used, 200 nursing students were randomly selected using convenience sampling, a self prepared knowledge questionnaire was use to collect the data. The findings showed that, 17 (8.5%) of the nursing students had inadequate level of knowledge, 172 (86.0%), had moderate level of knowledge, 11 (5.5%) had adequate level of knowledge; there was a significant association between the age and course of study with level of knowledge regarding hoarding disorder. In conclusion, findings of the study have implication for Nursing Practice, Nursing Education, Nursing Administration and Nursing Research.

Key words: hording disorder, student nurses and information booklet.

INTRODUCTION

Adolescence is a transitional stage of physical and psychological development that generally occurs during the period from puberty to legal adulthood¹. Hoarding disorder is an extreme disabling condition in which individuals have persistent difficulty parting with personal possessions, which results in clutter and inability to use the rooms in the home for their intended use. It causes public health problems when clutter attracts pest infestations or obstructs fire exits in apartment buildings, endangering both personal and neighbours' safety³. Hoarding often begins before adulthood; hoarding symptoms are more often mild, as opposed to moderate or severe, during childhood and adolescence⁴.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

A study to assess the knowledge regarding hoarding disorder among students of Jaipur Nursing College, Jaipur Rajasthan in a view to develop an information booklet.

OBJECTIVES

1. To assess the level of knowledge regarding hoarding disorder among students of Jaipur Nursing College.
2. To find the association between the knowledge score regarding hoarding disorder among students of Jaipur Nursing College with their selected socio demographic variables.

RESEARCH HYPOTHESIS

H0.1: There will be no significant association between the knowledge regarding hoarding disorder among the students with their socio demographic variables.

H1.1: There will be significant association between the knowledge regarding hoarding disorder among the students with their socio demographic variables.

REVIEW OR LITERATURE

A descriptive study was conducted to assess the prevalence of hoarding behaviour in the community among 742 participants from Baltimore epidemiological catchment area USA. Data was collected by using a semi-structured questionnaire. The result revealed that the prevalence of hoarding was nearly 4% and was greater in older than young age group, greater in men than in female, hoarding was associated with alcohol dependant, obsessive compulsive personality traits²⁴.

A co- relational study was conducted to assess the relationship between hoarding disorder and obsessive compulsive disorder among college student and community, hoarding was associated with higher scores on the Yale brown obsessive compulsive scale (YBOCS) in USA. The relationship was stronger among the community sample, in which there was a greater range of compulsive symptoms and hoarding behaviour. Among a sample of patients with obsessive compulsive disorder, 31% reported hoarding obsessive and 26% reported hoarding compulsions on Yale brown obsessive compulsive scale symptoms checklist. Result revealed that hoarding was the common symptom among obsessive compulsion disorders²³.

An epidemiological study was conducted to assess the estimate prevalence specific to DSM-5 hoarding disorder among 1698 adult individuals originally 10 recruited from South East London Community Health (SELCoH) home psychiatric interviews. Data was collected by self-report questionnaires. Result revealed that 19 individuals met DSM-5 criteria for hoarding disorder at the time of interview, corresponding to a weighted prevalence of 1.5%. Those with hoarding disorder were older and more often unmarried (67%). Members of this group were also more likely to be impaired by a current physical health condition (52.6%) or co-morbid mental disorder (58%), and to claim benefits as a result of these issues (47.4%)²⁷.

RESEARCH METHOD

Research approach

A quantitative evaluative research approach was adopted for the study.

Research design

An explorative descriptive research design was used in the present study

Research setting

The study was conducted in Jaipur Nursing College, Jaipur Rajasthan.

Accessible population

In the present study, the accessible population was nursing students in Jaipur Nursing College, Jaipur Rajasthan.

Sample

The sample for the study was nursing students in Jaipur Nursing College, Jaipur Rajasthan.

Sampling technique

Simple Random Sampling technique was adopted in the selection of sample for the purpose of the study.

Sample size

Sample size was 200 nursing students studying in Jaipur Nursing College, Jaipur Rajasthan.

Sampling criteria**Inclusion criteria**

1. B.Sc.(N), GNM, Post Basic B.Sc and M.Sc Nursing students studying in College of Nursing, who fulfil sampling criteria.

Exclusion criteria

1. The nursing students who were not present during the time of data collection.
2. The nursing students who were not willing to participate in the study

Description of the data collection tools

Part-i Socio-demographic variables: It consists of 9 baseline information of nursing students such as gender, age, religion, type of family, course of study, education status of father and mother, occupation of father and mother.

Part-ii Structured knowledge questionnaire to assess the level of knowledge regarding hoarding disorder. The copies of this tool were circulated among the experts in the field of three nursing experts and two psychiatrists. The final draft of the research study was finalized after incorporating the valuable suggestions by the experts. **Scoring:** The knowledge questionnaire regarding hoarding disorder was measured in terms of knowledge scores. There were 34 knowledge questions; each question had multiple choices in nature with 4 responses. Each correct answer was given a score of one and wrong answer zero. The maximum score was 34.

Validity of the tool**Content validity**

The valuable suggestion of experts was incorporated in the final preparation of the socio demographic and self structured questionnaire.

Reliability

Reliability of a research instrument is defined as the extent to which the instrument yields the same results on repeated measures. The tools were tested for reliability during the pilot study which was obtained by split half method by using Karl Person correlation coefficient and the score obtained was 0.6 so tool was considered to be reliable to proceed with the pilot study

Pilot study

The pilot study was conducted at Jaipur Nursing College, Jaipur Rajasthan, in the month of October 2021 to assess the feasibility of the study. 20 nursing students out of the total population was selected using Simple Random Sampling technique. The subjects for the pilot study possess the same characteristics as that of the samples for the final study but were not included in the main study. Prior to the study, permission was obtained from the concerned authorities. Following a brief self introduction, the selected respondents were informed about the purpose of the study and written consent was obtained. Assessment of the knowledge regarding hoarding disorder among students was done using the self structured questionnaire. The collected data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. After conducting the pilot study it was found that the study was feasible, the concerned authorities and subjects were cooperative, the tool was relevant, the time and cost of the study was within the limits.

Ethical consideration

The proposal for the study was approved by the Institutional Ethics Committee of Adesh University Bathinda, Punjab. Written permission was taken from Principal of Jaipur Nursing College, Jaipur Rajasthan. Anonymity and confidentiality of the data was assured, nursing students was informed that participation in the study was voluntary and they could withdraw from it at anytime. The students who were 28 interested in the study were asked to sign the consent form and fill the structured knowledge questionnaires and the return it to the researcher immediately, the routine classes of the students was not disrupted.

Procedure for data collection

Data collection was done in the month of November 2022, Sample of 200 nursing students who had enrolled in Jaipur Nursing College, Jaipur Rajasthan, selected by using simple random sampling technique. Formal permission was taken from the Principal, College of Jaipur Nursing College, Jaipur Rajasthan, for conducting the study. Informed written consent was taken from the sample after explaining the purpose of the study and data was collected by using a structured knowledge questionnaire.

Section I:

Table 1: Findings related to assessment of knowledge among nursing students of College of Nursing regarding hoarding disorder.

N=200			
Level of knowledge	Score	F	Percentage
Inadequate	0-11	17	8.5
Moderate	12-23	172	86.0
Adequate	24-34	11	5.5

Method of data analysis and presentation

It was decided to analyze the data using descriptive and inferential statistics on the basis of the study objectives and hypothesis; hence the collected data was carefully recorded, analyzed, summarized and tabulated through the SPSS.20

RESULTS AND TABLES

Organization and presentation of the data

The data collected were edited, tabulated, analysed, interpreted and findings obtained were presented in the form of tables and diagrams represent under following sections: **Section I:**

Table 1: Findings related to assessment of knowledge among students of College of Nursing regarding hoarding disorder.

Table 2-: Mean and standard deviation of level of knowledge regarding hoarding disorder among students of College of Nursing.

Section II

Table 3: Association between knowledge scores with selected Socio demographic variables.

Table-1: Depicts that 17 (8.5%) of nursing students had inadequate level of knowledge, 172 (86.0%), had moderate level of knowledge, 11 (5.5%) had adequate level of knowledge.

Figure 1: The Pie diagram shows the percentage distribution of nursing students according to the Level of Knowledge.

Table 2: Mean and standard deviation of level of knowledge regarding hoarding disorder among nursing students

Area	Mean score	Standard deviation
Knowledge	17.81	±4.021

Table 4. Revealed that the mean knowledge score regarding hoarding disorder was 17.8, and the Standard deviation was ±4.021.

Section II:

Table 3: Association between knowledge scores with selected Socio demographic variables.

Variables	Frequency	Mean	Std. Deviation	p Value
a) Age				0.002 S
17-20years	118	16.99	3.897	
21-24years	74	18.95	3.821	
25-28years	8	19.38	5.069	
b) Sex				0.044 NS
Male	25	19.32	3.288	
Female	175	17.59	4.077	
c) Religion				0.713 NS
Sikh	143	17.92	4.111	
Hindu	14	16.64	4.125	
Christian	2	17.00	8.485	
Muslim	41	17.85	3.539	
d) Type of Family				0.978 NS

Nuclear	149	17.81	4.119	
Joint	51	17.82	3.756	
e) History of family				0.899 NS
Yes	12	17.67	5.549	
No	188	17.82	3.923	
f) Course of study				0.001 S
I-G.N.M.	2	20.00	2.828	
II-G.N.M.	16	14.69	2.845	
III-G.N.M.	14	15.71	3.667	
I-B.Sc. (N)	43	16.93	4.026	
II-B.Sc. (N)	62	17.85	3.661	
III-B.Sc. (N)	27	20.22	4.163	
III-B.Sc. (N)	22	19.23	3.294	
I-P.B.B.Sc. (N)	4	14.00	4.243	
I-P.B.B.Sc. (N)	7	19.71	2.984	
I-M.Sc. (N)	3	23.00	1.000	
g) Area of residence				0.023 NS
Urban	59	16.81	4.200	
Rural	141	18.23	3.883	
h) Education Status of Father				0.555 NS
No formal education	11	16.36	3.828	
10 th standard	87	18.21	3.915	
12 th standard	55	17.58	4.425	
Graduation	40	17.50	3.789	
post graduation	7	18.71	3.773	
i) Education Status of Mother				
No formal education	14	17.50	4.864	0.701 NS
10 th standard	120	17.83	3.980	
12 th standard	40	17.30	4.008	
Graduation	18	18.94	3.572	
post graduation	8	18.13	4.549	
j) Occupation status of Father				0.464 NS
Shopkeeper	6	17.67	3.266	
Farmer	106	17.71	4.140	
Self employee	22	17.50	3.961	
Private employee	19	19.16	3.962	
Semi govt. Employee	3	21.00	2.000	
Government employee	37	17.70	3.865	
Retired person	7	16.00	4.359	
k) Occupation status of Mother				0.809 NS
House-wife	178	17.74	4.010	
Self employee	4	19.50	4.796	
Private employee	5	19.40	2.702	

Semi government employee	4	17.25	6.131
Government Employee	9	17.78	4.086

Table 3: shows the association between knowledge scores with the selected demographic variables reveals that there was statistically significant association among age (P=0.002) and course of study (P=0.001) with level of knowledge regarding hoarding disorder.

DISCUSSION

The study was conducted for about 4 weeks and data was collected from 200 nursing students by administering self structured questionnaire, Majority 172 (86.0%) of the nursing students had moderate knowledge followed by 17 (8.5%) who had inadequate knowledge and 11 (5.5%) had adequate level of knowledge regarding hoarding disorder. The overall mean for knowledge level of nursing students was 17.81 with a standard deviation of 4.021. The comparison of the knowledge scores of nursing students with their socio-demographic variables showed that there was a significant association between the level of knowledge regarding hoarding disorder with age (P=0.002) and course of study (P=0.001). Hence the null hypothesis ($H_{0.1}$) was rejected and the research hypothesis ($H_{1.1}$) was accepted. However, there was no significant association between the level of knowledge regarding hoarding disorder with sex, area of residence, Religion, type of family history, educational status of father, educational status of mother, occupation of father and occupation of mother.

CONCLUSION

The focus of this study was to assess the knowledge regarding hoarding disorder among students of Jaipur Nursing College, Jaipur Rajasthan, in a view to develop an information booklet. An Explorative Descriptive research design was used. The sample of 200 was drawn using probability simple random sampling technique. The data was collected by using a structured knowledge questionnaire and further analyzed and interpreted by applying statistical methods. The findings of this

study have implications in the field of nursing education, nursing practice, nursing administration and nursing research.

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